

3D Printing to Support Experimental Activities: Lessons Learned from Rapid Prototyping of an Electromechanical Actuator Gearbox

SPOKE 1 – Aerospace and sustainable mobility
Flagship Project – Space4You

PUBLICATION

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

3D PRINTING TO SUPPORT EXPERIMENTAL ACTIVITIES: LESSONS LEARNED FROM RAPID PROTOTYPING OF AN ELECTROMECHANICAL ACTUATOR GEARBOX

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ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing has been gaining widespread diffusion in the last few years, thanks to the availability of inexpensive desktop 3D printers based on Fused Filament Forming (FFF) and Stereolithography (SLA) technologies. Both in academic and industrial contexts, this technology can efficiently support the setup of laboratory activities, significantly reducing costs and time associated with the development of experimental test benches. For example, the design and manufacturing of custom fixtures and mock-ups can be significantly sped up, taking advantage of the unprecedented flexibility of desktop additive manufacturing machines. This work summarizes the use of FFF 3D printing for the development of a test bench intended to characterize the behaviour of an electromechanical actuator for aircraft flight controls. FFF 3D printing allowed to quickly manufacture a functional prototype of the actuators' main reduction gearbox. This complex assembly is one of the most critical components of an electromechanical servosystem, as its performances, in terms of efficiency, gear ratio, and reliability, dramatically influence the overall behaviour of the actuator.

Keywords: 3D printing; additive manufacturing; aircraft flight controls; electromechanical actuator;

1 INTRODUCTION

Electromechanical Actuators (EMAs) are a family of electrically powered devices employed to control the position of a mechanical component (i.e. the user). To do so, they usually include a permanent magnet servomotor with its control electronics, a mechanical transmission from the motor to the user, and a network of sensors to close the feedback loops. The application of EMAs is very common in the industrial automation and automotive fields, yet they are not widespread in aerospace systems, where electrohydraulic actuation still represents the industry standard. Indeed, EMAs can suffer from failure modes that are considered dangerous for a flight control actuator: specifically, their mechanical transmission may jam as a result of surface wear on its moving parts, and cause the actuator to get stuck in position [1-3].

This makes the installation of a backup actuator impractical, as the faulty one must be disconnected from the user by a dedicated system [4-6]. On the other hand, a flight control system based on EMAs would offer advantages compared to a more traditional electrohydraulic system, in terms of reduced weight and power consumption, as well as of easier maintenance: hence, electromechanical actuation technologies are getting more and more attention in the aerospace community [7, 8]. To mitigate the risks associated with EMA failure modes in flight control applications, advanced health monitoring and prognostic strategies are required. These involve the use of numerical models of the actuator either for real-time monitoring or for training surrogate emulators [9, 10]. To validate these numerical models, we developed a dedicated test bench (Figure 1) aiming to simulate on ground the operation of a flight control EMA. The test bench includes a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM) coupled to a Compound Planetary Gearbox (CPG). A high resolution incremental encoder is installed on the output of the gearbox, to enable closed-loop control of the user position. A host PC provides a user interface to control the actuator and logs all the measured data.

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A load simulation unit provides the external load to the actuator. This includes a disc brake, controlled in closed loop, coupled to the PMSM shaft upstream the CPG; additionally, the gearbox is loaded by a pair of elastic cables, whose force is measured by load cells. This arrangement allows to split the load paths for the motor and gearbox and permits to match the torque experienced by the two components with their capabilities, without worrying to accurately size the motor-gearbox coupling.

Figure 1 (a) Functional block diagram of the EMA test bench;
(b) Picture of the test bench.

One of the aims of the test bench design was to make extensive use of off-the-shelf components and rapid prototyping, in order to contain costs and time associated to hardware development, while at the same time allowing the system to be highly flexible and easily reconfigurable. In this context, emerging technologies enabling low-cost additive manufacturing provided an invaluable tool to speed up the development of the test bench. 3D printing, and specifically the Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) technology [11], is becoming more and more widespread as an affordable and flexible prototyping tool.

FFF printing relies on the deposition of a fused polymer, which is fed to the printhead in the form of a filament. Usually, the printhead moves in the x-y plane with respect to the workpiece; the latter is built one layer at a time, and is lowered once each layer is completed.

Several materials can be employed, including Polylactic Acid (PLA), Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS), Polyethylene Terephthalate (PETG), and Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU); specific applications, requiring higher heat resistance or higher stress, may employ Polyether Ether Ketone (PEEK). Brischetto and Torre presented an experimental characterization of the mechanical properties of 3D printed PLA in [12].

Ferro et al. [13] assessed the use of desktop 3D printers to manufacture multi-material panels. Approaches to improve the mechanical characteristics of high performance polymers printed with FFF technology is proposed by Han et al. [14] and Lederle et al [15].

The peculiar characteristics of FFF printing makes this process extremely flexible and able to deal with parts featuring almost arbitrarily complex geometries. Although 3D printing is inherently inferior to the more traditional injection moulding and machining processes in terms of achievable strength and surface finish, it allows speeding up dramatically the product design and iterative prototyping. For these reasons we made extensive use of FFF 3D printing during the development of the EMA test bench. This allowed to contain costs and reduce time associated to the design and manufacturing of components. Specifically, in this work we present the development of the planetary gearbox of the test bench: this subsystem includes a large number of moving parts, and is the most critical one among those manufactured through 3D printing, in terms of required tolerances, and involved speeds and powers.

2 DESIGN OF THE GEARBOX

The gearbox of the EMA test bench is a compound planetary drive with a Wolfrom arrangement [16, 17]. This specific architecture permits to achieve very high gear ratios (up to the order of 1000:1), with a mechanical efficiency comparable to cycloidal and harmonic drives [18], but requiring less strict tolerances than alternative solutions. In the aerospace field, Wolfrom drives are employed quite commonly for secondary flight control actuators [19, 20], or for electrically driven variable pitch propellers [21].

As shown in Figure 2, the gearbox is divided into an input stage and an output stage. The motor drives the sun gear of the input stage gear M, which meshes with the satellite gears S1. Those engage the fixed ring gear F, and move with the satellite gears of the output stage S2. The satellites S2 mesh with the output gear U, connected to the user (e.g. the control surface of the aircraft). As the input and output stages differ by a low number of teeth, the translation and peripheral speed of the satellites S2 do not compensate each other completely, and the output ring gear U is moved by the satellites.

Figure 2 Layout of the Compound Planetary Gearbox (CPG) of the EMA test bench.

Figure 2 shows the velocity distribution on the different wheels, and allows to compute the gear ratio that is, in the general case:

$$i = \frac{\frac{z_F}{z_M} + 1}{1 + \frac{z_F z_{S2}}{z_U z_{S1}}} \quad (1)$$

where z are the numbers of teeth of each wheel, denoted by the subscripts. If the input and output stages share the same modulus, Eq. (1) can be simplified as:

$$i = \frac{z_U}{z_M} \frac{2z_{S1}}{z_{S1} - z_{S2}} \quad (2)$$

This latter solution, which was employed in the test bench, simplifies the design but limits the achievable gear ratio to a smaller set of alternatives. The number of teeth used in our design is summarized in Table I, and yields a gear ratio of 124:1.

Table I - Number of teeth of the EMA CPG

z_M	21
z_{S1}	21
z_F	63
z_{S2}	20
z_U	62

The particular architecture employed in our application was discussed in [22-24]. In this particular implementation of a Wolfrom drive, the input stage is mirrored on the two sides of the output stages to balance tangential loads on the satellites. In addition, the use of helical gears with opposed helix angle and rolling rings (Figure 3) permits to balance completely axial and radial loads on the gears, eliminating the need for bearings and a planet carrier. With this solution, the gearbox has the configuration of a combined gear-bearing [25].

Figure 3 Cross-section of the CPG, highlighting the rolling rings and helical teeth

3 PRINTER AND SETTINGS

All the major components of the gearbox were manufactured with a FabTotum Core Pro 2018 desktop 3D printer. The machine features a single nozzle, an open chamber, and a heated deposition plate, an important element to mitigate thermal distortion of the components due to differential heating during printing. The printer is characterized by its simplicity of use, as the software for the management of the printing profiles provided by the manufacturers allows for a vast amount of controls to adjust the parameters of the machine, before and during processing. The parts were printed in PLA; this material, commonly employed for polymeric FFF printing, is characterized by a good strength at room temperature and a low thermal expansion. The low glass transition temperature means that the printed parts lose most of their strength at relatively low temperature, usually around 50°C.

This aspect is not considered detrimental for the considered application, as the low power dissipation of the gearbox is not expected to cause a significant temperature rise.

The layer height was set to 0.15mm, as a compromise between surface finish and printing time. The components were designed and printed with the layer lines parallel to the main direction of relative motion, to mitigate friction and wear. The infill of the parts is 25%, with four perimeters; as the parts have a small internal volume compared to their surface, this low infill value is considered sufficient.

4 ASSESSMENT OF PRINTER ACCURACY

Several causes can determine a discrepancy in dimensions between the source CAD file and the final printed part. The major ones that were observed affecting our prototyping process are listed below:

- *The thermal expansion of the printed material.* PLA is commonly chosen as a standard material for FFF 3D printing filaments; among the most important reasons are its low melting point and its low thermal expansion coefficient. The latter helps preventing the part from warping as the lower layers are in contact with the print bed, and the upper ones are near to the hot-end of the printer at a significantly higher temperature. Although, the small thermal expansion of PLA can still affect large parts, whose geometry makes them prone to warp, and which are required to fit into tight dimensional tolerances.
- *The local presence of over-extrusions or under-extrusions of material.* Even on a well calibrated machine, the surface finish of the printed part is relatively coarse due to the presence of layer lines and local variations of the quantity of extruded material. When printing fine features intended to fit precisely into a mechanical assembly, the overall effect is that the local over-extrusions will come in contact first. The parts will fit with an interference larger than expected, even if the average quantity of extruded material is right. To compensate for this, two solutions are usually possible: a post-processing of the part may be considered to improve surface finish (usually quite a time-consuming task); or, the behaviour of the manufacturing process can be accounted for in the design, setting the tolerance to looser values. In this latter case, a faster wear and a larger backlash should be expected if the printed components would experience high loads and relative velocities.
- *Nozzle positioning errors.* Most 3D printers use stepper motors to move the nozzle relative to the part along three axes. Usually, a reference position for each axis is found at the beginning of the print, and then the steppers are controlled in open loop. The actual position of the nozzle is not measured directly, but only estimated from the number of steps commanded to each motor. Several factors that are not accounted for by the control software may affect the actual nozzle position: for example, elasticity of the printer structure and transmission, backlash of the belts and leadscrews, and thermal expansion of the printer itself.

These effects introduce errors and reduce the accuracy of nozzle positioning, resulting in a printed part whose dimensions differ from nominal values.

To correct and compensate these effects, some tests were carried out to determine the capability of the printer to produce fine mechanical parts with tight tolerances. Before the actual prototyping of the gearbox, the tolerances of the machine were assessed by printing a pair of test gears. These included printed rolling rings similar to those present in the gearbox design (Figure 3), intended to bear radial loads and keep the gears at the right meshing distance.

In the original design of the test gears, the rolling rings and the actual gear wheel were intended to be printed as a single part (Figure 4(a)).

The result of this first iteration is shown in Figure 4(b): clearly, the need to support the bottom surface of the teeth and the top ring during the printing process yields a placement of support material that cannot be easily removed.

A possible solution would be to eliminate the 2 mm gap between the rings and teeth; however, such clearance is necessary to guarantee a fluid motion of the gears and avoid undesired interference between the rings and teeth. For this reason, this solution was ruled out.

The second iteration for the tolerance tests considered to split each gear wheel into three individual parts: the gear itself and the two rolling rings; this design included three pins on each ring and the corresponding holes on the gear to ensure a correct alignment of the parts.

This solution eliminated most of the overhangs of the parts, and allowed to print them without supports. The printed gear is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4 (a) drawing of the gear-rings part; (b) gear-rings printed as an individual component, highlighting the support material that is difficult to remove.

Figure 5 Gear and ring printed as separate parts to avoid support material.

Starting from a standard nominal sizing, several attempts were made to find suitable settings and to allow the gears to mesh at the nominal distance, with little to no backlash. Table 2 summarizes the sizing of three gear pairs; all the gears had 20 teeth, a pressure angle of 20° , 2mm modulus and 22.5° helix angle.

Table II - Dimensions of gears for tolerance tests

		Test #1	Test #2	Test #3
Primitive diameter	[mm]	40	40	40
External diameter	[mm]	44	43	43.4
Root diameter	[mm]	34	33	33
Circular tooth thickness/circular pitch		50%	40%	45%
Meshing distance	[mm]	42	<40	~40

The first test gears were designed with nominal dimensions, namely a circular tooth thickness to circular pitch ratio of 50%, a standard addendum equal to the modulus, and a slightly oversized dedendum 150% of the modulus. The printed parts resulted in a larger than nominal meshing distance of 42mm, that is they cannot mesh at 40mm without interference. The cause can be found in small, local over-extrusions that produce a part with slightly larger dimensions than the original CAD model. Reducing the extrusion flow may correct this issue, but would yield to globally under-extruded parts featuring poor mechanical properties. Therefore, we decided to tune the dimensions of the CAD model accounting for printing tolerances to achieve a dimensionally correct final part. Therefore, the second pair of test gears featured a circular tooth thickness to circular pitch ratio reduced to 40%, while the dedendum was increased to 175% of the modulus and the addendum reduced to 75% of the modulus. These gears were able to mesh at the nominal distance of 40mm; however, a noticeable backlash was introduced in the system.

In other words, the rolling rings came in contact before both sides of a tooth can touch the other gear.

While this situation may be acceptable for gears intended uniquely to transfer mechanical power, it is completely unsuitable for a servomotor, where a precise position control is needed and excessive backlash interacts negatively with the closed loop control law, yielding to dynamical instability and producing limit cycles.

The third pair of test gears have intermediate dimensions between the two previous tests: namely, the circular tooth thickness to circular pitch ratio was set to 45%, while the addendum and the dedendum were chosen as 85% and 175% of the modulus, respectively. This solution was suitable for a correct meshing at the nominal distance of 40mm, with little to no backlash.

Therefore, the corrections to the CAD geometry of the wheel calibrated with this preliminary test campaign were transferred to the global design of the planetary gearbox.

5 DESIGN MODIFICATIONS FOR MANUFACTURING TOLERANCES AND SUPPORT STRUCTURES

In addition to the correction of the gear sizing described in the previous section, the parts were adapted to minimize the use of support structures. The most complex component that required modifications of the design is the output ring gear. In the initial design iterations, it was modelled as a solid component including a double helical internal gear, an external spur gear, and interfaces for the metal rolling rings and external load simulator.

A preliminary manufacturing assessment of the design highlighted that the placement of support structures in close proximity of the gear teeth would result in a difficult support removal. Hence, the part was split into four sections as shown in the exploded view of Figure 6.

Figure 6 Exploded view of the output ring gear.

The double helical gear teeth are printed separately from the outer shell of the output ring. In addition, the two output lugs are printed individually and glued to the shell with epoxy resin, as their supports would interfere with the external crown. The internal and external rings are mounted without glue, as torque is transferred through the straight teeth spline visible in Fig. 6. The axial positioning of the internal ring is guaranteed by the two metal rolling rings, which in turn are secured in place by 20 self-threading screws, set into reinforced zones of the shell.

6 ASSEMBLY AND INTEGRATION

The assembly of Compound Planetary Gearboxes is often a complex process as the planet gears shall be synchronized to ensure a correct timing between the multiple satellites meshing the same sun and ring gears. At first, the three satellites and the output ring gear were pre-assembled. Each satellite includes planet gears and spacers, mounted on a 12 mm square steel torque tube. An M8 threaded rod passes through the torque tube, securing the assembly with a castellated nut and split pin on one end, and a self-locking nut on the other end. The proper synchronization between the three gears of each satellite is guaranteed by a mark that allows to easily identify the orientation of each wheel during the assembly process. Figure 7 compares the CAD render and the picture of an assembled satellite.

Figure 7 CAD render (top) and picture (bottom) of an assembled satellite gear.

The three satellites are placed inside the first fixed ring gear, with the corresponding sun wheel; the correct timing of the satellites is guaranteed by placing the gears 120° apart while checking the position of the orientation marks. Then, the output ring gear is installed, followed by the middle section of the sun gear. The assembly is completed by installing the last ring gear and completing the sun gear. The latter cannot be pre-assembled, as it locks in position and ensures the stability of the satellites. The modular construction of the wheels allowed to complete the assembly of the transmission without relying on the flexibility of components or having to split the ring gears, which may have resulted in an irregular transmission of torque. The assembled planetary drive is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Picture of the completed gearbox.

7 CONCLUSIONS

A functional prototype of the main reduction gearbox of an aircraft actuator test bench was developed making extensive use of FFF additive manufacturing. The process highlighted the advantages of this technology and its ability to support the quick development of experimental setups. In addition, this activity allowed to learn how to adapt a design to the actual capability of the additive manufacturing machine and obtain mechanical parts able to fit together and operate smoothly, with low friction and low backlash. The test bench is currently being employed to validate high-fidelity digital twins of the actuator, and to assess the performance of real-time diagnostics and health monitoring algorithms.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

In conclusion, the authors would like to acknowledge the Inter-Departmental Center of Photonics of the Politecnico di Torino (PhotoNext) and PNRR-NODES - Spoke 1 - Topic Aerospace for their support. Additionally, we extend our thanks to engineers Guido and Giorgio Riva from CAMAR S.p.A. for the technical and operational assistance throughout the entire prototype development and the related final assembly process.

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